

**ATMOSPHERIC AND CHEMICAL ANALYSIS
OF BLUE STRAGGLER POPULATIONS IN
NGC 3201**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Gourav Kumawat**, BS-MS (Physics), has worked on the project entitled ‘**Atmospheric and Chemical Analysis of Blue Straggler Populations in NGC 3201**’ under my supervision and guidance.

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ABSTRACT

Globular clusters are among the oldest stellar systems, consisting of tens of thousands of stars that are located at the same distance from us and move together in space. Due to their high stellar densities, frequent gravitational interactions occur within them, leading to several dynamical processes that give rise to exotic stellar populations. One such population is that of Blue Straggler stars (BSSs): stars that appear to lag behind in stellar evolution and are rejuvenated via some mechanism of mass transfer.

This thesis delves into the analysis of atmospheric parameters, such as effective temperature and surface gravity, and the determination of chemical abundances of the BSS populations in the globular cluster NGC 3201. The open-source framework `iSpec` was employed to analyze spectra of 62 BSSs obtained from the Michigan/Magellan Fiber System (M2FS) mounted on the Magellan Clay Telescope. The derived parameters revealed various characteristics of BSSs, with particular emphasis on fast rotators. The fast rotators were observed to be located in the upper-left region of the BSS sequence, exhibiting higher radial velocities and effective temperatures. Additionally, the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ was found to increase with decreasing temperatures of the BSSs, indicating a rise in opacity with an increase in iron content. The orbital parameters for four of the BSSs were obtained from previous studies, further suggesting coalescence in multiple-star systems as a possible formation mechanism for fast rotators. Analyzing the atmospheric parameters and chemical abundances of BSSs in this manner has the potential to offer valuable insights into the mechanisms accountable for the formation of these exotic stellar objects. Consequently, this contributes significantly to our understanding of stellar evolution and adds to the broader comprehension of globular clusters.

LIST OF SYMBOLS OR ABBREVIATIONS

AGB	Asymptotic Giant Branch
BSS	Blue Straggler Star
CCD	Charged Coupled Device
CMD	Color Magnitude Diagram
DEC	Declination
T_{eff}	Effective Temperature
FOV	Field Of View
GC	Globular Cluster
GMCs	Giant Molecular Clouds
HB	Horizontal Branch
HRD	Hertzsprung-Russell Diagram
HST	Hubble Space Telescope
HUGS	HST Ultraviolet Globular Cluster Survey
LTE	Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium
M2FS	Michigan/Magellan Fiber System
MSTO	Main Sequence Turn Off
MS	Main Sequence
MT	Mass Transfer
OC	Open Cluster
RGB	Red Giant Branch
RA	Right Ascension
RLOF	Roche Lobe OverFlow
$v \sin(i)$	Rotational Velocity
M_☉	Solar mass
SGB	Sub-giant Branch
log g	Surface Gravity
UV	Ultraviolet
WDs	White Dwarfs

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*In this dynamic world, which resembles a globular cluster, I dedicate
this thesis to my parents, the most exotic binary stars I know of...*

Chapter 1

Introduction

All the stars in the cosmos start their saga from the gravitational collapse of Giant Molecular Clouds (GMCs). Some form as individuals, while the most form in a group gravitationally interacting with other stars. Eventually, the pressure and temperature in the cores of these collapsing fragments suffice to start thermonuclear reactions, and a star is born, destined to follow an evolutionary pattern in the Hertzsprung-Russell Diagram (HRD).

1.1 Star Clusters

Star clusters consist of hundreds to thousands of stars that share the same distance from us and move together in space. They are considered the fundamental building blocks of galaxies ([4]) and play a crucial role in their formation and chemical evolution ([10]).

Martin G. H. Krause ([34]) defined a cluster as a group of stars inside a closed tidal surface, satisfying the following conditions:

1. The group of stars should be gravitationally bound. If they are not gravitationally bound, they are referred to as associations.
2. The cluster volume should not be dominated by dark matter. If it is dominated by dark matter, it would resemble a galaxy's condition.
3. The cluster must contain at least 12 stars to avoid confusion between star clusters and multiple-star systems.

Star clusters can be classified into two primary types (Figure 1.1):

1. **Open Clusters (OCs):** These clusters have no definite shape and are relatively young, ranging from a few million years to a few billion years. They are less massive (less than $10^5 M_{\odot}$) and contain fewer stars (less than 10,000). They are mostly situated near the Galactic plane, and our Milky Way harbors thousands of them.
2. **Globular Clusters (GCs):** These clusters have a definite spherical shape and are relatively old, with an age exceeding 10 billion years. They are more massive (more than $10^4 M_{\odot}$) and contain a larger number of stars (more than 10,000). They are mostly located near the Galactic Halo, and our Milky Way contains over 150 of them.

Figure 1.1: Left: GC Messier 80. Right: OC Pleiades. (Credits: NASA)

1.2 Globular Clusters

As discussed in Section 1.1, our Milky Way alone hosts over 150 GCs. The study of these GCs has become the pinnacle of research in the field of astronomy, significantly influencing various areas of astronomical research. GCs serve as indicators for the structure and history of the Milky Way. The dynamics of GCs provide a research ground for studying the classical gravitational n-body problem, with recent increases in computational capability greatly advancing this field. Additionally, GCs continue to serve as a natural laboratory for studying stellar formation and evolution, considering the constraints on the age, distance, and chemistry of stars

within a cluster. Whether clusters are viewed as single entities, collections of interacting point masses, or sets of complex evolving stars, they hold vital importance in modern astronomy ([5]).

It has been discovered that the overall progression of a cluster is regulated by the exchange of energy among individual stars, binary systems, and the cluster as a whole ([5]). This energy transfer can manifest in various forms. Interactions between binary stars and other members of the cluster can transfer energy between the internal motions of the binary system's constituents and the entire cluster ([28]). The formation and dissolution of binaries can directly and indirectly impact the cluster's dynamics by altering the characteristics of the binary star population. Moreover, stellar mass loss influences cluster dynamics by modifying the cluster's gravitational potential ([25]). Understanding the outcomes of these effects necessitates a deeper understanding of the internal properties of the involved stars that transcends the point-mass approximation. Also, the ultra-dense cores of GCs provide an optimal environment for producing exotic stars such as blue stragglers (see Chapter 2), most of which are believed to be products of binary system evolution, originating and/or consolidating through stellar interactions. In recent decades, Charged Coupled Devices (CCD) cameras have completely transformed the field of GCs, enabling new areas of investigation that rely on high-resolution imaging and spectroscopy ([60]).

1.3 Stellar Evolution

The HRD is a scatter plot of stars illustrating the relationship between a star's Absolute Magnitude/Luminosity vs Effective temperature/Spectral Classification. The HRD is considered the holy grail of Stellar Astronomy, as it can depict all the evolutionary stages of a star and provide significant insights into stellar physics. Figure 1.2 demonstrates how stars of different masses traverse the HRD. Low-mass stars go through the sub-giant branch (SGB), red giant branch (RGB), and asymptotic giant branch (AGB) phases, while high-mass stars experience yellow, blue, and red supergiant phases.

In this thesis, our focus is solely on low-mass stars ($< 8 M_{\odot}$). These stars initiate their journey as T-Tauri stars and progress to the Main Sequence (MS), where they spend the majority of their lifespan ([33]). During the MS phase, they burn hydrogen to helium through proton-proton chain reactions. As the stars consume hydrogen in their core, helium accumulates, and since helium cannot undergo fusion, the core contracts. This compression raises the core's density and pressure.

Figure 1.2: Evolutionary tracks for single stars in the mass range of 0.5–60 M_{\odot} , illustrating the different phases that each star undergoes. (Credits: Wikipedia Commons)

The heat released from this compression fuels H-shell burning. The resulting He-ash from H-shell burning accumulates in the core, increasing its mass and intensifying H-shell burning. The resulting radiation pressure from H-shell burning causes the stars to expand, resulting in a decrease in surface temperature. The star transitions to the SGB, and the convective envelope provides energy, slowing down the star's expansion. The further expansion of the star occurs at a constant surface temperature. The star almost moves vertically in the HRD, becoming a red giant ([65]). However, the expansion during the RGB phase comes at a cost, with the star losing approximately 30 % of its mass through stellar winds due to the weak gravitational force experienced by the outermost layers and high radiation pressure.

After the RGB phase, the fate of the star is determined by the mass of its He core ([32]). Stars with initial masses below 0.5 M_{\odot} lack the necessary temperature for He core burning, leading to their evolution into He-core white dwarfs (WDs). The cores of stars with initial masses between 0.5 to 3 M_{\odot} undergo electron degeneracy

before He burning begins, as a result of extensive contraction. This degeneracy allows the core temperature to rise (to approximately 10^8 K) without a corresponding increase in pressure, triggering a runaway He-burning process known as He flash. Stars exceeding $3 M_{\odot}$ do not undergo degeneracy and instead initiate He burning in the core via the triple-alpha process in a quasi-equilibrium manner. As the He burning process stabilizes in the core, the H burning shell cools down, reducing surface luminosity. The star then moves almost horizontally towards the bluer side in the HRD along the Horizontal Branch (HB) ([66]). As He depletes in the core, He burning commences in the shell near the core, causing the star to move along a branch asymptotic to the RGB but with higher luminosity and lower surface temperature. This stage is referred to as AGB. Ultimately, at the end of the AGB phase, stars lose much of their mass and form a planetary nebula illuminated by a hot central core. This hot central core is known as the carbon-oxygen (CO) core WD. Figure 1.3 summarises the various evolutionary stages for a low-mass star.

Figure 1.3: The evolutionary journey of a $1 M_{\odot}$ star, starting from its initiation as a hydrogen-burning main-sequence star and concluding with its transformation into a white dwarf. Essential core structural changes are depicted at pivotal stages. (Credits: The Cosmic Perspective by Jeffrey O. Bennett)

Chapter 2

Blue Straggler Stars

As discussed in Section 1.2, GCs are amazing laboratories for studying stellar evolution and host many exotic stellar populations. One such population is Blue Straggler Stars (BSSs): *the stars that seem to lag behind in stellar evolution*.

In GCs, BSSs are identified as stars positioned to the left and above the main-sequence turnoff (MSTO) in the optical color-magnitude diagram (CMD, see Figure 2.1). However, considering the ages of GCs, it is anticipated that these stars would have transitioned off the main sequence and evolved into red giants long ago ([60]), evident from their higher temperatures and luminosities compared to the MSTO, also indicating their higher stellar masses ([5]; [63]).

Due to their higher mass compared to the average cluster stars, BSSs are likely affected by dynamical friction and mass segregation, causing them to sink towards the cluster core ([41]; [15]). Furthermore, the dense core of the cluster facilitates frequent stellar interactions, promoting both the formation and consolidation of binary systems, thus contributing to the generation of BSSs. Therefore, investigating the characteristics of BSSs can offer valuable insights into the dynamical evolution of the host cluster and provide critical information on the progenitor stellar population and binary systems ([5]; [15]).

2.1 Historical Background

Sandage ([52]) first discovered BSSs in the globular cluster M3 in 1953 as part of his PhD thesis. While examining the CMD properties of M3 (see Figure 2.1), he noticed a group of stars situated above the main sequence, suggesting they were younger than the majority of the cluster stars. During this early period, the nature of BSSs remained largely unknown, leading to the development of various speculative theories to explain their significance. For nearly two decades, M3 stood

as the only compelling example of a GC with BSSs until the photometric study of the metal-rich GC M71 in 1971 ([3]). Interest in BSSs experienced a resurgence with the discovery of BSSs in NGC 5466 ([48]). By 1992, there was a significant shift, with over 400 BSSs identified in more than 20 GCs ([53]; [20]).

Figure 2.1: Sandage’s first CMD of M3. BSSs and MS branch are labelled. (Credits: [52])

Notably, two significant advancements revolutionized the observation of Blue Straggler Stars (BSSs) ([5]). The first breakthrough involved the adoption of CCD detectors for BSS searches. The benefits of the linear digitized images produced by CCDs outweighed the limitations of a narrow field of view (FOV) when studying stellar populations in GCs. Equally crucial was the integration of algorithms such as DAOPHOT ([62]) or DOPHOT ([56]), which accurately determined magnitudes for overlapping stellar images. This combination of hardware and software enabled the generation of deep CMDs, crucial for identifying blue stragglers and conducting more precise photometry in the densely populated inner regions of clusters.

The onset of the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) represented a significant advancement in BSSs studies, benefiting from its unparalleled spatial resolution and capabilities in ultraviolet (UV) imaging/spectroscopy ([26]). Exploration of the BSS population in UV CMDs marked a pivotal moment, as optical CMDs of old stellar populations were predominantly populated by cooler stars. This posed challenges in observing and compiling comprehensive samples of hot stars in the optical band. Despite the progress made with HST, systematic examination of BSSs in

optical bands remained challenging, particularly in the dense central regions of high-density clusters.

Nevertheless, BSSs posed an intriguing and unresolved puzzle for several reasons: they filled a critical gap in the understanding of stellar evolution, particularly regarding binary systems; the formation pathways expected from binary evolution likely operated in galactic fields as well, emphasizing BSSs as a component of galaxy populations that is often overlooked; and their blue hues significantly impacted the UV photometry of unresolved galaxies, necessitating the inclusion of their frequencies into synthesis stellar population models ([60]). Recent compilations of BSSs in optical bands encompass nearly 3000 candidates across 56 GCs ([51]).

2.2 Formation Pathways

The position of BSSs in the CMD (see Figure 2.1), suggests that they are more massive than the current cluster members. This is further supported by previous mass measurements ([58]; [24]; [19]). However, GCs are completely devoid of gas, making any recent star formation practically implausible ([1]). As a result, the origin of BSSs should be associated with a mechanism that results in an increase in the initial stellar mass through a rejuvenation process. Figure 2.2 summarizes the three primary formation mechanisms of BSSs.

Mass Transfer

McCrea ([42]) proposed that Mass Transfer (MT) from a binary companion could rejuvenate the acceptor star and result in the formation of a BSS. The efficiency of MT depends upon orbital periods: wide orbits yield conservative MT, leaving behind a remnant, whereas close binaries may undergo non-conservative MT, potentially leading to mergers ([32]). Furthermore, MT's efficiency depends on the masses of the stars involved and the influence of their surroundings, making it a complex process. Therefore, understanding the evolutionary phase of stars at the onset of MT is pivotal in understanding the eventual outcomes. The initiation of MT is characterized by Roche Lobe Overflow (RLOF). The Roche Lobe represents the gravitational equipotential surface of a binary star system. If the stellar material of the donor star remains within its Roche lobe, its gravitational force prevails, and no MT occurs. However, if the donor star evolves to the point where it touches its Roche lobe, the gravitational force of the acceptor star becomes influential, triggering MT from the donor to the acceptor via the L1 Lagrangian

Figure 2.2: BSS Formation Pathways (Credits: Snehalata Sahu)

point (see Figure 2.3). Typically, the donor star is more massive and evolves more rapidly than the acceptor star.

The MT process is categorized into three main types based on the evolutionary phase of the donor star ([2]):

- Case A: MT takes place when the donor star in a close binary overflows its Roche lobe during core hydrogen burning (MS stage).
- Case B: MT occurs when the donor star overflows its Roche lobe during hydrogen burning in a shell around its core (RGB stage).
- Case C: MT takes place when the donor star overflows its Roche lobe during helium burning in its core (Supergiant stage).

Depending on the type of MT, the binary system evolves into a BSS and a WD with lower (Case A/B MT) or normal mass (Case B/C MT) ([32]). This distinction arises because in Case B and C MT, the donor star's core is already established, thereby leaving the final evolutionary outcome of the donor star unaffected by the MT process. The resulting BSS+WD system may undergo another MT event if the BSS fills its Roche lobe, but a merger is unlikely, given the system's survival of a previous MT phase, resulting in a WD+WD system. The mass of the donor WD

Figure 2.3: Mass transfer through Roche Lobe Overflow via L1 Lagrangian point. (Credits: Pearson Prentice Hall, Inc, 2005)

depends upon the donor star’s mass, while the accretor WD mass is influenced by the BSS’s mass, which surpasses the original accretor star’s mass. Case C MT leads to the formation of a CO core WD, whereas Case B MT yields a He core WD.

In instances where binary stars are sufficiently close for Case A/early Case B MT yet distant enough to prevent merger, a BSS+WD system can emerge. However, in this scenario, the donor’s core is not fully developed before MT begins. Consequently, mass loss during MT results in a lower-mass WD. This phenomenon can give rise to low-mass WDs ($< 0.4 M_{\odot}$), which cannot form through isolated star evolution within the age of the universe ([11]). The detection of such low-mass WDs can validate the Case A/B MT pathway as a plausible formation mechanism for the BSS.

Collisions

Individual stars have the potential to collide or merge in close binary systems, resulting in a final star of higher mass ([29]; [36]). Collisions between two MS stars can produce BSSs. These physical collisions often take place in the dense cores of star clusters, with a majority occurring while the stars are on the MS. Due to the relatively low relative speeds of stars within stellar clusters compared to their surface escape speeds, collisions between two MS stars typically result in their merger with minimal mass loss ([1]). The remnants of such collisions are intricate, accompanied by uncertainties. However, merger products typically

exhibit relatively higher angular momentum, leading to rapid rotation and a non-spherical shape. Internal mixing within the merger product is crucial, particularly concerning the replenishment of the core with unburned hydrogen and subsequent calculations of the merger product's lifetime.

Encounters involving binary stars can occur as frequently as those involving single stars. Although binaries constitute a small fraction, their increased collision rate with single stars, owing to a larger cross-section, compensates for this. Stellar collisions are more probable in a subset of encounters involving binaries, potentially resulting in the formation of BSSs. In less-dense clusters, stellar collisions during encounters between two binaries become particularly significant ([1]).

Hierarchical Triple Systems

Another collisional mechanism arises as a consequence of the very long-term evolution of hierarchical triple star systems. If the eccentricity of the inner pair of stars in a hierarchical triple stellar system increases through interaction with the outer component, a merger of the inner binary will occur ([46]). This is likely to result in a MS+BSS binary with long eccentric orbits. Perets & Fabrycky ([50]) proposed that such mergers of the inner binary play a significant role in the formation of BSSs in OCs. The study of physical stellar collisions during the very long-term evolution of hierarchical triple and quadruple star systems, including perturbations due to passing stars, is an area that calls for further investigation. In this thesis, our central focus revolves around exploring the mechanisms of mass transfer and collisions as drivers for BSSs formation. Initially, it might appear that these two processes are entirely independent; however, in reality, they are often intertwined. Collision events leading to the formation of BSSs are frequently facilitated by binaries, much like how mass transfer can be initiated following the hardening of a binary during a close encounter ([30]). The observed population of BSSs in most GCs likely arises from a combination of both these mechanisms. Additionally, mass transfer is anticipated to play a more significant role in less-dense environments such as OCs and in the galactic halo.

Therefore, the unresolved nature of the problem surrounding BSSs holds paramount importance in accurately modeling binary populations and their evolutionary paths. Furthermore, it is crucial within the realm of stellar dynamics, which serves as the cornerstone for understanding the theory of dense stellar systems ([60]).

2.3 Chemical Abundance of BSSs

The absence of a single formation scenario capable of explaining all observed BSSs across different clusters necessitates the identification of distinguishing characteristics for each formation scenario. An evident indicator proposed in the literature is chemical abundance. Detailed calculations employing smooth particle hydrodynamics to study stellar collisions have revealed that the merged object remains relatively unmixed, displaying surface abundances consistent with the envelope abundances of the most massive star ([37]). Conversely, during binary mass transfer, the deeper layers of the donor star are exposed and accreted last, resulting in surface abundances for the blue straggler that bear the signatures of chemical processing, particularly partial hydrogen burning.

Measuring surface abundances in BSSs discovered in GCs presents challenges due to their faintness. Nonetheless, recent studies have endeavored to determine the chemical composition of these objects, offering insights into their formation history. For instance, in the case of 47 Tuc, Ferraro ([16]) delved into the chemical composition of its BSSs and identified a notable number of stars exhibiting depletion in carbon (C) and oxygen (O). Such C-O depleted BSSs are anticipated if, during their formation, they accreted CNO-processed material from their binary companions. Hence, these chemical anomalies may directly indicate a mass-transfer mechanism ([60]). Intriguingly, 47 Tuc remains the only cluster where such a high prevalence of depleted BSSs has been observed. Conversely, in clusters like M4, M30, and ω Centauri, only one to two stars with a notable C-O signature have been identified ([39]; [38]; [45]). Considering the limitations of small number statistics, the compiled data confirm that the percentage of CO-depleted BSSs is small (on the order of 10 %; [1]). This suggests that either the mass transfer formation pathway is not highly efficient in GCs, or the anticipated surface depletion of C and O in this scenario may be a transient phenomenon ([16]).

In a separate study, Pasquini ([49]) conducted a chemical abundance analysis of a BSS in Palomar 12 using high-resolution spectroscopy and LTE (Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium) analysis of ESPRESSO spectra. Their research suggested that lithium abundance could serve as a discriminative factor among different BSS formation mechanisms. However, the obtained 3σ abundance of Li, which exceeded 3.1, proved inconclusive for drawing a definitive inference.

It is clear that the problem of BSS formation is far from being fully understood, and it is therefore fundamental to perform similar chemical analyses, including other elements, of BSSs in larger samples of GCs, significantly increasing the sample

statistics ([60]).

2.4 Fast Rotator BSSs

The rotational velocity distribution of the BSSs may serve as another potential indicator of the formation mechanism involved. Rotational velocity ($v \sin(i)$) is a measure of how fast a celestial object, such as a star or a planet, is rotating. The $v \sin(i)$ notation specifically refers to the projected rotational velocity. This means that the observed velocity is not the true rotational velocity of the object, but rather the component of the rotational velocity that is projected onto the line of sight of the observer. The inclination angle, i , represents the angle between the rotation axis of the object and the line of sight from the observer's perspective (see Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: Illustration showing the distinction between the observed rotational velocity ($v \sin(i)$) and the true rotational velocity (v). (Credits: Cambridge University Press; [67])

Ferraro ([18]) analyzed 320 high-resolution spectra of BSSs in eight GCs with different structural characteristics and provided evidence that the fraction of fast-rotating BSSs increases as the central density of the host system decreases. The fast rotators (FRs) were defined as the BSSs with $v \sin(i) \geq 40$ km/s. Although the threshold is arbitrary, they showed that by choosing slightly different thresholds (e.g., 30 or 50 km/s), the overall results remain unchanged ([7]).

The observational findings suggest that FRs are approximately one order of magnitude less abundant (about 4 %) in high-density clusters compared to low-density

clusters (about 38 %). FRs in low-density clusters are likely formed by MT in binary systems. In both BSS formation mechanisms, resulting BSSs are claimed to have high rotational velocities. In the case of MT in binary systems, angular momentum is also transferred to the acceptor ([54]), while in collisions, proto-BSSs rapidly contract, conserving their angular momentum ([6]). However, in later stages of evolution, braking mechanisms such as magnetic braking, disk locking, and mass loss are expected to intervene and slow down the stars, with timescales and efficiencies that are still poorly understood ([59]).

Although collision rates are low in low-density clusters, reducing the chances of BSS formation through collisions, low-density environments are effective in preserving primordial binaries for recent BSSs formation. This is evident from the higher fractions of binaries present in low-density environments compared to high-density ones. Consequently, FRs are found in significant numbers in low-density environments. Conversely, in high-density systems, the relatively fewer number of FRs can be attributed to the destruction of primordial binaries by stellar interactions and efficient braking mechanisms acting on collisional BSSs.

Thus, the rotational distributions of the BSSs are related to the binary fraction and the local density of the cluster. FRs also serve as indicators of recent MT events. This characteristic is essential for constructing models and interpretative scenarios that can provide crucial information on BSS physics and possibly their formation mechanisms as well. It also provides insights into the effects of stellar interactions in collisional systems like GCs.

Chapter 3

NGC 3201

NGC 3201 (see Figure 3.1) is a low galactic latitude halo GC in the southern constellation of Vela. The right ascension (RA) and declination (DEC) of the cluster center are $10^h, 17^m, 36.82^s$ and $-46^\circ 24' 44.9''$, respectively. It is also known as Caldwell 79. The cluster has an age $\approx 12.2 \pm 0.5$ Gyr ([43]), a distance ≈ 4.9 kpc, metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.59$ dex, and reddening ≈ 0.24 ([27]).

Figure 3.1: Left: Image of NGC 3201 by the HST with a $3.5'$ view. Right: Color-composite image of NGC 3201, obtained with the WFI instrument on the ESO/MPG 2.2-m telescope at La Silla Observatory. (Credits: Wikipedia Commons)

This cluster exhibits an unusually high radial velocity (≈ 490 km/s) in relation to the Sun, exceeding that of any other known cluster. Its orbit is retrograde, indicating rapid movement in the opposite direction to the galactic center. The distinctive behavior of this cluster suggests the possibility of extragalactic origins, eventually captured by the gravitational force of the Milky Way ([57]). Nonetheless, the stars within this cluster display a chemical resemblance to those found in other galactic GCs, suggesting a shared formation point in both space and time. Whether it was

assimilated by our galaxy or evolved independently from its original cluster family, this cluster remains a captivating subject for further investigation.

3.1 Previous Studies

The composition of stars within NGC 3201 displays heterogeneity, varying as one moves away from its core. Stars located farther from the core exhibit higher effective temperatures, while redder and cooler stars are predominantly found near the cluster’s center. Despite being a less dense GC and showing no signs of core collapse, the observed inhomogeneity is thought to be associated with a population of black holes in its core. Indeed, several black holes have been identified within this cluster, orbiting in close proximity to neighboring stars ([22]). A study conducted in 2022 ([70]), utilizing data from HST and Gaia, revealed the motion of stars near the cluster’s core, indicating the presence of a sub-cluster consisting of stellar-mass black holes, totaling $\approx 1000 M_{\odot}$.

Previous studies have explored the potential dispersion in [Fe/H] abundance among giant stars in NGC 3201, attributing it to the influence of non-LTE effects driven by iron overionization in the spectroscopic analysis. Consequently, this dispersion doesn’t reveal anything unusual about the cluster ([44]). B. Giesers ([23]) delved into the examination of binary star compositions in the core of NGC 3201 using radial velocity variations, revealing that at least 57.5 ± 7.9 % of BSSs exist in a binary system. Alex Billi ([7]) employed high-resolution spectra obtained with the Magellan Telescope to determine the radial and rotational velocities of around 200 stars in NGC 3201. The surveyed sample includes BSSs and reference stars in different evolutionary stages (MSTO, SGB, RGB, and AGB) (see section 3.2 for more details).

To the best of our knowledge, a comprehensive examination of chemical abundances in BSS populations within this cluster appears to be lacking.

3.2 BSS Spectra

In this thesis, we utilized 62 BSSs spectra obtained from the multi-object fiber system Michigan/Magellan Fiber System (M2FS), which feeds the double spectrograph MSPec mounted on the Magellan Clay Telescope at the Las Campanas Observatory in Chile. The spectra were acquired as part of the proposal CN2019A-15, with Principal Investigator Lorenzo Monaco. The M2FS instrument enables the simultaneous observation of up to 128 objects per spectrograph over a FOV of

about 30' in diameter. The data were collected in February-March 2019 through 16 repeated exposures in the spectral region 5127-5184 Å, with a spectral resolution of 18000. This resolution allows to adequately sample the first two lines of the Mg triplet at 5167.3 Å and 5172.6 Å. Two distinct fiber configurations were utilized to obtain spectra for roughly 200 targets in the direction of the cluster. A total of six exposures, each lasting 30 minutes, were acquired on the first night, while 10 exposures, each lasting 20 minutes, were obtained on the second night ([7]).

The BSSs spectra, along with their corresponding ID, RA & DEC, and $v \sin(i)$ values, are accessible on Cosmic-lab¹. Alex Billi ([7]) provides a detailed description of the data reduction process and their methodology for determining radial velocity, cluster membership, atmospheric parameters, and $v \sin(i)$ values for the BSSs. The continuum-normalized and radial velocity-corrected spectra (zoomed to see Mg lines closely) of 62 BSS stars are presented in Figure 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5 respectively.

3.3 BSS candidate selection

Alex Billi ([7]) conducted the BSS selection based on high-resolution ultraviolet catalogs obtained from HST observations for the central regions of NGC 3201 and optical ground-based catalog observations for the external regions ([17]). To determine the positions of BSSs on the CMD, we cross-matched the RA and DEC provided by them with the HST UV Globular Cluster Survey (HUGS, [47]) catalog for BSSs in the inner region and the Gaia EDR3 catalog ([21]) for BSSs in the outer region of the cluster. This resulted in 27 BSSs crossmatched with HUGS data and 35 BSSs crossmatched with Gaia data. The resulting CMDs can be found in Figure 3.6 and 3.7. The ID, RA, DEC, visual magnitude, and cluster membership probability for the BSSs can be found in Table 3.1. The spatial locations of the BSSs in the different regions of the cluster can be found in Figure 3.8, Figure 3.9, and 3.10 respectively.

¹http://www.cosmic-lab.eu/Cosmic-Lab/BSS_rotation.html

Table 3.1: Details of the BSSs studied in this thesis. The BSS IDs are named such that smaller numbers correspond to BSSs closer to the cluster’s core. The Cosmic-Lab IDs are the ones provided for the corresponding BSSs on their website. RA and DEC are directly taken from the Cosmic-Lab website. The absolute magnitude (M_v) is calculated by subtracting the apparent visual distance modulus ($(m-M)V = 14.20$, [27]) from the apparent visual magnitude (V). The apparent visual magnitude (V) is obtained by crossmatching the BSSs positions with the photometric catalog of the Stetson database ([61]). The cluster membership probabilities (PROB) are obtained from [47] and [69].

BSS ID	Cosmic-Lab ID	RA (degrees)	DEC (degrees)	M_v	PROB (%)
B1	1012746	154.4033625	-46.4136813	2.57	97.2
B2	1023539	154.3993515	-46.4078560	3.34	97
B3	1013700	154.3962520	-46.4182565	3.07	96.9
B4	1022302	154.4098273	-46.4102006	2.73	97.8
B5	1012904	154.4019237	-46.4198272	2.03	97.3
B6	1014355	154.3911378	-46.4196159	3.07	97.1
B7	1025211	154.3849299	-46.4076830	3.38	97.3
B8	1021152	154.4195717	-46.4093147	2.97	97.3
B9	1025619	154.3816172	-46.4041477	2.66	99.9
B10	1005074	154.4006768	-46.4278998	2.84	97.2
B11	1031149	154.4004033	-46.3970078	2.49	97.7
B12	1010831	154.4189046	-46.4216023	2.14	97.3
B13	1021331	154.4184729	-46.4027317	3.19	97.7
B14	1009786	154.4276377	-46.4137044	2.75	97.7
B15	1020369	154.4272846	-46.4087656	3.00	97.1
B16	1031222	154.3994121	-46.3927124	3.38	97.7
B17	1026151	154.3766105	-46.4000632	3.57	97.2
B18	1016643	154.3700469	-46.4114471	3.02	97.1
B19	1006762	154.3834415	-46.4321004	2.40	97.3
B20	1009269	154.4330228	-46.4137157	2.44	97.5
B21	1016923	154.3668729	-46.4150062	3.62	97.4
B22	1002749	154.4246075	-46.4282995	3.40	97.3
B23	1019708	154.4337343	-46.4011820	3.37	97.6
B24	1008650	154.4390510	-46.4182480	3.25	95.3
B25	1030901	154.4032020	-46.3843063	3.27	100
B26	2716018	154.3760880	-46.4361699	2.99	100
B27	2713289	154.3947502	-46.4416678	3.10	13.7

Continued on next page

B28	1017509	154.3594693	-46.4223802	1.66	100
B29	2717902	154.3607599	-46.3985450	2.69	100
B30	2718774	154.3527168	-46.4121898	1.99	99.9
B31	2711709	154.4041397	-46.4461522	3.54	0.06
B32	2717877	154.3609053	-46.3881454	1.66	100
B33	1035238	154.3842813	-46.3772396	3.18	100
B34	2714632	154.3860264	-46.4501061	2.23	100
B35	2705123	154.4507866	-46.4315920	2.41	100
B36	2713191	154.3951283	-46.3726009	2.51	100
B37	2705506	154.4472108	-46.3887971	3.34	99.9
B38	2711800	154.4035545	-46.4540524	2.59	100
B39	2714006	154.3898416	-46.3689811	3.31	100
B40	2704041	154.4626969	-46.4327815	2.88	0
B41	2709841	154.4152943	-46.3652141	3.39	99.9
B42	2714772	154.3851443	-46.4635956	2.95	100
B43	2720497	154.3341108	-46.4439012	2.29	100
B44	2710692	154.4103191	-46.4691207	3.16	100
B45	2711836	154.4034550	-46.4747336	3.05	99.9
B46	2600533	154.3140993	-46.3867423	2.99	100
B47	2702518	154.4824695	-46.3775296	2.43	100
B48	2707141	154.4338850	-46.3495438	3.05	96.5
B49	2601312	154.3002520	-46.4078210	3.63	100
B50	2717272	154.3667567	-46.4837663	3.65	99.9
B51	2601851	154.2893054	-46.4032201	3.26	100
B52	2715664	154.3784331	-46.3332489	2.42	100
B53	2708408	154.4249930	-46.3192117	3.22	100
B54	2602084	154.2836336	-46.3533481	3.51	99.9
B55	2717413	154.3656112	-46.5290841	3.39	100
B56	2603587	154.2407347	-46.4623012	3.45	99.9
B57	2602689	154.2683715	-46.3318255	2.30	59.1
B58	2603838	154.2324762	-46.3496011	3.16	100
B59	2714749	154.3855481	-46.5545236	3.00	100
B60	2301092	154.2432987	-46.2935999	2.65	0
B61	2801544	154.6364229	-46.4157168	3.44	100
B62	2201091	154.4436556	-46.2464918	3.34	100

Figure 3.2: NGC 3201 BSS spectra (B1-B16) with continuum-normalized and radial velocity-corrected. The spectrum is zoomed in to closely examine the Mg lines. The Mg₅₁₆₇ and Mg₅₁₇₃ lines used for radial velocity determination are also shown with black dashed and dotted lines, respectively.

Figure 3.3: NGC 3201 BSS spectra (B17-B32) with continuum-normalized and radial velocity-corrected. The spectrum is zoomed in to closely examine the Mg lines. The Mg₅₁₆₇ and Mg₅₁₇₃ lines used for radial velocity determination are also shown with black dashed and dotted lines, respectively.

Figure 3.4: NGC 3201 BSS spectra (B33-B48) with continuum-normalized and radial velocity-corrected. The spectrum is zoomed in to closely examine the Mg lines. The Mg₅₁₆₇ and Mg₅₁₇₃ lines used for radial velocity determination are also shown with black dashed and dotted lines, respectively.

Figure 3.5: NGC 3201 BSS spectra (B49-B62) with continuum-normalized and radial velocity-corrected. The spectrum is zoomed in to closely examine the Mg lines. The Mg₅₁₆₇ and Mg₅₁₇₃ lines used for radial velocity determination are also shown with black dashed and dotted lines, respectively.

Figure 3.6: V_{606} vs $V_{606} - I_{814}$ CMD from the HUGS data on NGC 362. The blue star markers indicate 27 BSSs crossmatched in the inner region of the cluster. The fast rotator BSSs are encircled red.

Figure 3.7: G_{mag} vs $G_{\text{BP}} - G_{\text{RP}}$ CMD from the Gaia EDR3 data on NGC 362. The grey stars represent those with a cluster membership probability greater than zero. The blue star markers indicate 35 BSSs crossmatched in the outer region of the cluster. The fast rotator BSSs are encircled red. Regarding the three BSS candidates lying near the MSTO (B31, B37, & B50), we checked for any other plausible BSS candidate near that location but couldn't find any within $3''$. Although their positions are not completely off the MSTO, we still considered them because they have already been classified as BSSs in previous studies ([7]).

Figure 3.8: HST F606W image of the core of NGC 3201 taken by the HST ACS Wide Field Camera on March 14, 2006, with a total exposure time of 5 seconds ([47]) and a FOV of $5' \times 5'$. The 27 BSSs candidates are highlighted with red circles of a $3''$ radius and labeled with their IDs (smaller numbers correspond to BSSs closer to the core). Most of these sources are located within the cluster's core radius ($1.3'$) of the cluster, as indicated by the blue circle labeled r.c.

Figure 3.9: ESO/MPG 2.2m telescope image of NGC 3201 in the V/89 filter taken by wide field imager (WFI) with a total exposure of 480 seconds (credits: ESO Imaging Survey) and a FOV of $10' \times 10'$. The 23 BSSs candidates are marked with red circles of a $3''$ radius and labeled with their IDs (smaller numbers correspond to BSSs closer to the core). Most of these sources are situated between the core radius ($1.3'$) and half-mass radius ($3.1'$) of the cluster, as indicated by the blue circles labeled r_c and r_h, respectively.

Figure 3.10: UK Schmidt telescope image of NGC 3201 taken on March 4, 1978 with a total exposure of 4200 seconds and a FOV of 23'x23'. This image is sourced from the DSS survey produced at the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI). The 12 BSS candidates are marked with red circles of a 3'' radius and labeled with their IDs (smaller numbers correspond to BSSs closer to the core). Notably, all the sources are located outside the cluster's half-mass radius (3.1'), as indicated by the blue circles labeled r_h.

Chapter 4

Methodology

We utilized `iSpec` ([8]; [9]) for spectral analysis in our work. `iSpec` is an integrated spectroscopic software framework designed for determining astrophysical parameters (including effective temperature, surface gravity, metallicity, etc.) and individual chemical abundances. This open-source code¹ is mainly written in Python and can be used on different platforms. The methodology for the spectral analysis is outlined in this chapter. We have also included examples of methodology testing that we performed to validate our analysis during the initial phase of this thesis.

4.1 Continuum Normalization

Continuum normalization of a spectrum involves the process of removing or flattening the underlying continuum level of the spectrum, revealing the relative variations in the spectral features more clearly. The continuum represents the broad, smooth background of a spectrum, and normalizing it helps in emphasizing the absorption or emission lines and other finer details.

`iSpec` works only on the normalized spectra, which helps us to avoid worrying about the underlying physical unit of the fluxes of spectra as well. Before performing continuum normalization, we need to convert the spectra into a format compatible with `iSpec`. This format employs a text file with tab characters as column identifiers. The data should contain three columns: wavelength, flux, and flux error. In cases where the flux error is unknown, it can be set to zero (as in the case of BSS spectra of NGC 3201).

The continuum points within a spectrum are identified by applying a median and maximum filter with varying window sizes. The median filter smoothens out noise, while the maximum filter disregards deeper fluxes associated with absorption lines

¹<https://www.blancocuaresma.com/s/iSpec>

([8]). This process results in the placement of the continuum slightly above or below the original locations based on user-defined parameters. Subsequently, a polynomial or a set of splines (as selected by the user) is employed to model the continuum. Finally, the spectrum is normalized by dividing all flux values by the modeled continuum.

In the case of BSS spectra from NGC 3201, we observed prominent emission peaks in the spectra that could affect the continuum fit. To address this, we utilized `scipy.signal.find_peaks` to remove these emission peaks from the spectra before continuum normalization.

4.2 Radial Velocity Correction

Radial velocity refers to the velocity of an object along the line of sight of an observer. It is the component of an object’s velocity that is directed either toward or away from the observer. Radial velocity is often measured using the Doppler effect, which involves the shift in wavelength of spectral lines due to the motion of the object.

In astronomy, radial velocity is commonly used to study the motion of celestial objects, such as stars, galaxies, and planets. When an object is moving toward an observer, its spectral lines shift toward shorter wavelengths (blueshift), and when it is moving away, the lines shift toward longer wavelengths (redshift) (see Figure 4.1). This information is valuable for understanding the dynamics, orbits, and interactions of astronomical objects.

The radial velocity for spectra can be determined by calculating wavelength shifts for prominent lines such as the Mg triplet and Hydrogen Balmer lines. The spectrum can be shifted by considering the determined radial velocity (v) to convert observed wavelengths (λ) to rest wavelengths (λ_{corr}) using the following formula (4.1):

$$\lambda_{corr} = \lambda \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v}{c}}} \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.2 provides an example of radial velocity determination for HST/STIS 800-resolution BSS spectra, conducted as part of testing our methodology.

For the case of NGC 3201 BSS spectra, the radial velocity was determined using the first two lines of the Mg triplet at 5167.3 Å and 5172.6 Å. Previous studies ([7]) suggest that the radial velocities should be close to 500 km/s. Notably, for certain spectra, only the Mg 5167Å line provided the correct radial velocity value,

which was closer to 500 km/s. Consequently, we utilized only that line instead of the average value obtained from the two Mg lines.

4.3 Synthetic Spectral Fitting Method

Synthetic spectral fitting is a method used in astrophysics to analyze the properties of stars by comparing observed spectra with theoretical spectra generated through models. This method involves comparing the observed spectrum with synthetic spectrum generated on-the-fly ([68]), focusing on specific spectral features. Utilizing a least-squares algorithm (Levenberg–Marquardt, see Equation 4.2), we minimize the differences between the synthetic and observed spectra.

Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm: Given a set of m empirical pairs (x_i, y_i) of independent and dependent variables, find the parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ of the model curve $f(x, \boldsymbol{\beta})$ so that the sum of the squares of the deviations $S(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is minimized. In our case, m is the number of spectral data points we have under consideration for fitting, x_i is wavelengths, and y_i is their corresponding flux points. $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ can be an array of atmospheric parameters (like temperature, metallicity, surface gravity, etc.) or abundance values for each elemental spectral line, and $f(x, \boldsymbol{\beta})$ is the function representing the model spectral flux points. Thus, $S(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ represents the sum of the squares of the deviation between observed and model spectra points, which is to be minimized.

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \in \operatorname{argmin}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}} S(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \equiv \operatorname{argmin}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \sum_{i=1}^m [y_i - f(x_i, \boldsymbol{\beta})]^2 \quad (4.2)$$

In each iteration, the algorithm modifies a single free parameter while determining the optimal direction for the adjustment. The spectral characteristics being analyzed may involve absorption lines or other spectral segments. For instance, it's typical to utilize features within regions such as H α , H β , and the Mg triplet to remove parameter degeneracies, given their sensitivity to effective temperature and surface gravity ([9]). Synthetic spectra are produced as needed by interpolating from a grid of model atmospheres using a radiative transfer code.

Synthetic spectral fitting is a powerful tool for extracting detailed information about stars from their observed spectra. It aids in determining the star's spectral type and luminosity class based on observed spectra, and it is instrumental in extracting fundamental stellar parameters such as temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity. Additionally, it provides abundance estimates of elements present in a star by fitting individual spectral lines. Lastly, this method can be applied to

analyze the stellar population within a galaxy or a star cluster

4.3.1 Radiative Transfer Code

A radiative transfer code is a computational tool utilized in astrophysics to model the propagation of radiation through a medium, often in the form of electromagnetic waves such as light. The primary objective of a radiative transfer code is to simulate how radiation interacts with matter, including absorption, emission, and scattering processes. The code is based on the principles of radiative transfer, involving the tracking of energy transport through a medium, which could be the interstellar medium, stellar atmospheres, or circumstellar material. It solves the radiative transfer equation, describing the balance between the absorption, emission, and scattering of radiation within a medium. Radiative transfer codes commonly employ numerical methods, such as Monte Carlo simulations, finite-difference methods, or other computational techniques to approximate solutions. These codes account for various physical processes, including line absorption, continuum opacity, and scattering by particles or molecules. Additionally, they may consider the effects of magnetic fields, temperature gradients, and other relevant physical properties. Radiative transfer codes are crucial in synthetic spectral fitting, generating synthetic spectra based on theoretical models by simulating the interaction of radiation with the medium, including computing absorption and emission features in the spectrum.

`iSpec` provides a diverse range of radiative transfer codes, and in this thesis, we utilized the `SYNTHE` radiative transfer code ([35]; [55]). Specifically designed for synthesizing stellar spectra, `SYNTHE` simulates radiative transfer processes in stellar atmospheres. It is implemented in `FORTRAN` and requires the Intel compiler, thus pre-compiled executables are provided by default within `iSpec` ([9]). The code operates under the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE), where the mean free path of photons is smaller than the scale over which thermodynamic quantities vary. In LTE, transfer equations are solved by assuming a blackbody source function, resulting in atmospheric conditions (such as temperature) at a given depth being influenced by radiation both below and above that point. The model atmospheres employed in `SYNTHE` are calculated with plane-parallel geometry, enabling the solution of radiative transfer while disregarding atmospheric curvature and considering only one depth variable. `SYNTHE` excels at generating high-resolution synthetic spectra featuring detailed line structures, essential for accurately reproducing observed spectral characteristics in stellar spectra. The code utilizes extensive line lists for various elements, ensuring a comprehensive

treatment of absorption and emission lines across the spectrum.

4.3.2 Model Atmosphere

A model atmosphere is essential for determining the thermodynamic properties required for calculating abundances. Constructed based on four fundamental physical parameters describing a star—Effective temperature (T_{eff}), surface gravity ($\log g = \log(\frac{GM}{R^2})$), metallicity ($[M/H]$), and microturbulent velocity (v_{mic}) — these models are foundational tools in astrophysics, particularly for studying stellar atmospheres. Model atmospheres provide a theoretical framework to understand and interpret observed spectra of stars. Within a model atmosphere, a temperature profile describes how temperature varies with depth into the stellar atmosphere, while the pressure within the atmosphere is specified as a function of depth. The distribution of matter, or density profile, is also a crucial parameter in a model atmosphere. Incorporating information about the chemical composition of the stellar atmosphere, including the abundance of various elements, model atmospheres account for opacity due to different elements and molecules in the form of absorption lines. The abundances significantly impact opacities and spectral features. Line opacities are essential for synthesizing realistic spectra, encompassing both the absorption lines and continuous processes such as electron scattering and free-free absorption contributing to the continuum opacities. Model atmospheres serve as the foundation for generating synthetic spectra. The physical parameters and chemical composition specified in the model atmosphere are used to calculate the expected intensity of radiation at different wavelengths.

`iSpec` includes various grids of model atmospheres, such as MARCS GES/APOGEE and ATLAS9 Kurucz/Castelli/Apogee/Kirby models. In this work, we specifically utilized the model named `ATLAS9.KuruczODFNEW` which incorporates the Kurucz opacity distribution functions (ODF) with improvements ([12]). The Kurucz ODFs represent wavelength-dependent opacities due to various atomic and molecular transitions in the stellar atmosphere. The use of opacity distribution functions allows for a detailed treatment of line opacity, considering a range of temperatures, pressures, and chemical abundances.

Parameter ranges for `ATLAS9.KuruczODFNEW` are: $T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ to 50000 K, $\log g = 0$ to 5 (cgs) with different masses and radii, $[M/H] = -2.5$ to 0.5 , with $[\alpha/Fe] = 0.0$ and 0.4 , and v_{mic} fixed at 2 km/s.

4.3.3 Atmospheric Parameters

In the analysis of NGC 3201 BSS spectra, atmospheric parameters were determined using the `ATLAS9.KuruczODFNEW` model atmosphere with the `SYNTH` radiative transfer code in `iSpec`. Two approaches were employed: one using Mg lines and the other using Fe lines (see Table 4.3). The initial parameters for effective temperature (T_{eff}) and surface gravity ($\log g$) were set to 7700 K and 4 dex, respectively, based on the range quoted in previous research (6700-8700 K for T_{eff} and 3.6-4.3 dex for $\log g$; [7]). The metallicity (M/H) was fixed at -1.6, matching the cluster’s $[Fe/H]$ value obtained from the Harris catalogue ([27]). The $v \sin(i)$ values were sourced from Cosmic-Lab². The final T_{eff} and $\log g$ values were derived as the means of those obtained from Mg and Fe lines, with the corresponding standard deviations serving as errors.

Table 4.1 presents a comparison of atmospheric parameters derived from our analysis with those listed in the Kepler dataset. This comparison was performed for five LAMOST low-resolution spectra ($R \sim 1800$) of RGB stars, as part of the testing of our methodology.

Table 4.1: Comparison between the effective temperatures and surface gravities derived from spectral analysis using `iSpec` and those provided in the Kepler survey for five LAMOST low-resolution spectra ($R \sim 1800$) of RGB stars.

Kepler ID	Kepler Survey		iSpec	
	T_{eff} (K)	$\log g$	T_{eff} (K)	$\log g$
10000108	4804	3.287	5209 ± 159	3.74 ± 0.44
10000207	4810	3.79	4970 ± 217	3.85 ± 0.58
10000547	5059	3.414	5170 ± 180	3.96 ± 0.49
10000981	4871	3.569	5260 ± 365	4.14 ± 1.05
10001326	4776	2.96	5000 ± 175	3.39 ± 0.45
10001440	4931	3.184	5084 ± 217	3.32 ± 0.62

4.3.4 Chemical Abundances

In astronomy, all chemical elements heavier than hydrogen and helium are collectively referred to as ”metals”. Their abundance is quantified using the ”abundance ratio”, which is defined as the logarithm of the ratio of two metallic elements in a star relative to their ratio in the Sun. For instance, the abundance ratio of magnesium to iron ($[Mg/Fe]$) is expressed as in Equation 4.3:

$$[Mg/Fe] = \log_{10}(Mg/Fe)_{star} - \log_{10}(Mg/Fe)_{sun} \quad (4.3)$$

²http://www.cosmic-lab.eu/Cosmic-Lab/BSS_rotation_catalogs.html

Within `iSpec`, the determination of chemical abundance relies on a solar abundance reference. Firstly, various line regions associated with a particular element are chosen. Solar absolute abundances for these selected lines are acquired using reference atmospheric parameters. Then, absolute abundances for these same selected lines are determined from the spectrum being analyzed. Relative abundances are computed by subtracting the solar absolute abundances from the absolute abundances obtained from the analyzed spectrum. The ultimate abundance for the spectrum is established by computing the average value, with the standard deviation regarded as the internal error ([8]).

In the analysis of NGC 3201 BSS spectra, we determined the chemical abundances using three approaches:

- Initially, we determined the abundance of all elements by combining the spectral lines. For elements such as Ni, Na, and Cu, where only one line is available (Table 4.3), line-by-line abundance derivation and error calculation were not feasible.
- Subsequently, for Mg and Ti, which have two lines each (Table 4.3), we performed line-by-line abundance analysis. The final abundance was obtained by calculating the mean, with the standard deviation representing the errors.
- In the case of Fe, a total of 10 lines (Table 4.3) were available for analysis. Abundance values were determined for each line individually, and subsequently, the mean and standard deviation were calculated to represent the abundance value and error, respectively. Initially, extreme values were observed, prompting a closer examination of the data. It was identified that some cases exhibited extreme values, adversely affecting the results. To address this issue, a refinement process was introduced. The obtained values were pruned based on range: -1 to -3. Within the range, the mean and standard deviation were recalculated. This refinement was applied to mitigate the impact of extreme values on the overall results. This pruning process was guided by the recognition that the cluster's $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ value is -1.6. Unfortunately, a similar approach couldn't be applied to other elements due to the availability of only two lines per element for analysis.

Table 4.2 provides a comparison between the abundance results obtained in our analysis and those from the LAMOST survey. This comparison was conducted for medium-resolution spectra with $R \sim 7500$, as part of the testing of our methodology.

Table 4.2: Comparison between the abundance ratios derived from spectral analysis using *iSpec* and those provided in the LAMOST survey for two medium-resolution spectra ($R \sim 7500$). The precision of abundance values in the LAMOST survey ranges from 0.05 to 0.20 dex ([71]). Within this error limit, our values closely match those in the survey for most of the elements. Some discrepancies may arise due to insufficient absorption lines for abundance calculation, unresolved lines, or improper line fitting.

Abundance	58025-HIP507401_sp04-141		58216-hip6672501_sp04-062	
	LAMOST	<i>iSpec</i>	LAMOST	<i>iSpec</i>
[Ti/Fe]	-0.12	-0.11	-0.06	0.01
[Cr/Fe]	-0.08	-0.01	-0.01	0.00
[Ni/Fe]	0.12	0.02	-0.04	0.00
[Mg/Fe]	0.17	0.14	0.15	0.01
[Si/Fe]	0.14	0.09	0.19	0.03
[S/Fe]	0.52	0.53	0.4	1.86
[Al/Fe]	0.21	-0.17	-0.01	-0.25
[Ca/Fe]	0.26	-0.4	0.2	0.01
[Cu/Fe]	0.23	0.45	0.51	0.41
[C/Fe]	-0.11	0.45	-0.37	0.73
[O/Fe]	0.16	3.94	0.2	0.43

Table 4.3: Details of the Spectral Lines for Various Elements provided in *iSpec* and used in NGC 3201 BSS spectra analysis.

Element	Peak Wavelength (nm)
Cu	515.323
Na	514.884
Ni	513.036
Mg	516.732
	517.2684
Ti	512.916
	515.407
Fe	512.736
	513.147
	513.266
	513.679
	514.174
	515.084
	515.191
	516.628
516.903	
	517.160

Figure 4.1: Illustrated above is the 'wobble' induced in a star's motion due to the gravitational influence of a planet as they both orbit around a common center of mass. This orbital dance results in the star exhibiting apparent motion towards and away from the observer. In the upper scenario, the star is approaching the observer, causing a blueshift in its spectra. Conventionally, in such cases, the star is assigned a negative radial velocity. In the lower scenario, the star is receding from the observer, resulting in a redshift in the spectra. Conventionally, in this context, the star is attributed a positive radial velocity. (Credits: ESA)

Figure 4.2: The top panel displays the HST/STIS spectra of a BSS in M3. The left figure exhibits the original spectra in red and the continuum fit in green. The right figure illustrates the normalized spectra with various lines employed for radial velocity calculation. In the bottom panel, each line is shown zoomed in, along with the corresponding radial velocity calculated from the line. Note that the radial velocities are similar for all lines except H δ . This disparity is due to an unresolved peak in the H δ line.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussions

Using the methodology provided in the previous chapter (4), we performed spectral analysis of the BSSs in NGC 3201. The results of our analysis are presented in this chapter. We have also attempted to draw physical inferences to explain any significant trends found among the derived properties of the BSSs.

5.1 Derived Properties of BSSs

The atmospheric parameters (T_{eff} and $\log g$) derived from the spectra for all 62 BSSs are provided in Table 1 along with derived radial velocities (RV) and obtained $v \sin(i)$ values from Cosmic-Lab. The chemical abundances of the 62 BSSs are also provided in Table 2.

Figure 5.1 provides insights into the obtained T_{eff} and $\log g$ values and their corresponding errors. Previous studies ([7]) quoted the T_{eff} and $\log g$ in the range of 6700-8700 K and 3.6-4.3, respectively. Most of our derived values are also in the same range with some differences, which may be accounted for by the fact that the previous studies used isochrone fitting on the CMD locations of the BSS to get the atmospheric parameters. Meanwhile, we have used a different approach, where we derived atmospheric parameters using synthetic spectral fitting on Mg and Fe lines. Most of the errors in T_{eff} fall within 600 K of standard deviation. Most of the errors in $\log g$ are also within 0.2 dex standard deviation.

Figure 5.2 provides insights into the obtained chemical abundances and their corresponding standard deviation errors. Since, to our knowledge, this is the first time an abundance analysis has been performed in the BSSs in NGC 3201, we do not have any previous studies to compare our results with. However, the obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ value can be compared with the cluster's $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ value of approximately -1.6. More than 50 % of the BSSs have $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ values in the range of -1.3 to -1.9.

Figure 5.1: Histograms of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and the standard deviation errors in them ($\sigma_{T_{\text{eff}}}$ & $\sigma_{\log g}$) obtained as atmospheric parameter estimations of BSSs in NGC 3201 (see Table 1).

Figure 5.2: Histograms of the chemical abundances estimated for Ni, Cu, Na, Mg, Ti, and Fe of BSSs in NGC 3201 (see Table 2). In the bottom panel, the histograms of the standard deviation errors estimated for chemical abundances in Mg, Ti, and Fe are also shown.

There is a significant spread of [Fe/H] values around the cluster’s [Fe/H] value, as can be seen in the [Fe/H] histogram. Regarding the standard deviation errors in [Mg/Fe], [Ti/Fe], [Fe/H], we can see that most of the errors are within 0.5-0.6 dex, which is decent considering the resolution of 18000 and fewer number of lines to work on.

Figure 5.3 illustrates the $v \sin(i)$ distributions as a function of absolute visual magnitude (M_v) and color (V-I) for the BSSs. The apparent visual magnitude (V) and color (V-I) are obtained by crossmatching the BSSs positions with the photometric catalog of the Stetson database ([61]). The absolute magnitude (M_v) is then calculated by subtracting the apparent visual distance modulus ($(m-M)_V = 14.20$, [27]) from the apparent visual magnitude (V). There is no clear trend

Figure 5.3: Left: Plot of $v \sin(i)$ versus absolute visual magnitude (M_v) of the BSSs. Right: Plot of $v \sin(i)$ versus color (V-I) of the BSSs. The fast rotator BSSs are encircled red.

observed between M_v and $v \sin(i)$. However, in the V-I vs $v \sin(i)$ plot, it is noticeable that the fast rotators (FRs, $v \sin(i) > 40$ km/s) tend to have V-I < 0.75 . This implies that the FRs are predominantly located at the bluer end of the CMD. This is further confirmed by the locations of the FRs in NGC 3201 CMDs (Figure 3.6 & 3.7).

Figure 5.4 reveals how different atmospheric parameters (& radial velocity) vary with one another. There are some interesting trends observed. Firstly, the BSS with larger radial velocity (RV > 510 km/s) are all FRs. Secondly, it is also evident that the FRs have higher surface temperatures ($T_{\text{eff}} > 8000$ K). Also, the BSSs with larger RVs also have higher surface temperatures ($T_{\text{eff}} > 9000$ K). Notably, we also observed that there is no visible trend of any atmospheric parameter with $\log g$, which seems to be understandable as surface gravity doesn't play a key role in the mass transfer process.

Figure 5.5 reveals how chemical abundances of different elements vary with atmospheric parameters ($v \sin(i)$, T_{eff} , & $\log g$). First of all from Figure 5.2, we can see that there is not much dispersion in the abundance values for BSSs in most of the cases. Adding on to that, the errors are significant enough that no prominent trend can be observed with full confidence. In the case of Na, Ni, and Cu, we do not have error estimates as well, as only one line each element was available. Moreover, there are possibilities of non-LTE effects, which were not taken into account by the LTE assumptions in *iSpec*. However, one particular trend is that

with an increase in surface temperature the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ decreases.

5.2 FRs tend to be located towards the upper left side of the BSS sequence

The previous study ([7]) also revealed in their analysis that the FRs are found in the upper left side of the BSS sequence in NGC 3201. This trend has also been observed in other clusters as well (M4, M30; [40]). It is also generally accepted that BSSs located towards the upper left side of the BSS sequence are more massive. Under the hypothesis that BSS rapid rotation in low-density environments is mostly due to MT in binary systems ([18]), this suggests that the most recent BSS formation activity preferentially involved more massive primordial binaries. This may be further confirmed by the fact that the majority of the FRs are in the core ($2/3$ of them lying within $1.6 \times r_c$). NGC 3201 has an intermediate dynamical age, suggesting that the mass segregation process is happening, due to which heavier stars sink towards the cluster center, which may result in heavier BSSs. A previous study has also confirmed a radial increase of the binary fraction towards the cluster centre due to mass segregation ([23]).

5.3 FRs tend to have higher radial velocities

We observed imperfect fitting of the Mg lines in the FRs with RVs > 510 km/s. The previous study ([7]) also mentions that cluster members with RVs larger than the average are rapidly rotating BSSs, for which the measurements are more uncertain due to the significant deformation of the absorption lines. Thus, larger RVs do appear to be a signature of deformed absorption lines. However, they may also be caused by orbital motion in binary systems. At least one of the FRs with higher RV, B6, is a confirmed binary system, as detailed in Table 5.1. The orbital motion in binary systems may explain the larger RVs for other FRs within the cluster's core. For FRs in the outer region, the possible explanation for such larger RVs may be three- and four-body interactions that occurred in the cluster core, resulting in the origin of fast rotators that were subsequently ejected to the external regions at high speeds ([39]). Although NGC 3201 has not experienced a core collapse, it has an intermediate relaxation time ($\log T_{rel} \text{ yr}^{-1} = 9.27$; [72]), suggesting a not very efficient internal dynamical evolution. However, NGC 3201 does have abnormal black hole populations ([22]) in the core, which may contribute to the interactions

Figure 5.4: Scatter plots showing how different atmospheric parameters estimated for BSSs in NGC 3201 vary with each other. The data points are shown in blue and underlying error bars are depicted in sky-blue. The fast rotator BSSs are encircled red.

Figure 5.5: Scatter plots showing how chemical abundances for different elements vary with $v \sin(i)$, T_{eff} , and $\log g$. The data points are depicted in blue, with underlying error bars shown in sky-blue. The fast rotator BSSs are encircled red.

leading to larger RVs in FRs in the outer region of the cluster.

5.4 FRs tend to have higher temperatures

The previous study ([7]) employed isochrone fitting on the CMD locations of BSSs to identify a similar trend of increasing temperature in FRs. We demonstrated the same trend with temperatures estimated from spectral analysis. The higher temperatures for FRs support our previous finding that FRs tend to be on the upper left side of the BSS sequence. As discussed before, FRs are likely formed in recent MT events from more massive primordial binaries in less-dense environment. This trend of increasing rotation in higher temperature objects is also observed in MS stars, which is associated with their reduced convective envelopes, leading to significantly lengthened spin-down times ([7], and references therein). This results in an increase of radiative transfer of energy and thus, higher surface temperatures. Under the hypothesis that NGC 3201, being a loose cluster, should have the majority of BSSs formed by MT, a similar process may explain the trend of higher temperatures in FRs. The collisional products are not expected to develop a convective envelope ([59]). This association of rotation with mass, CMD location, and temperature may provide valuable insights for improved BSS models.

5.5 Variation of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ with effective temperature

We observed a decrease in temperature with increasing $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, suggesting a correlation between metallicity and stellar temperature. This decrease may be attributed to the rise in opacity caused by the abundance of partially ionized iron and its bound-bound transitions. Bound-bound transitions refer to processes in which electrons in atoms or ions transition between different discrete energy levels. These transitions occur when an electron absorbs or emits a photon, leading to a change in the electron's energy level within the atom or ion. The higher metal content, particularly an increase in iron content, may lead to a greater number of transition lines available for photon absorption, which increases the opacity. The increased opacity resulting from these bound-bound transitions facilitates the trapping of heat or absorption of radiation within the stellar atmosphere, inducing a cooling effect on the star. While other elements in the iron group may also contribute to opacity, their combined abundance is typically more than an order of magnitude lower than that of iron. Consequently, they do not significantly contribute to the overall increase in opacity observed with higher metallicity ([31]).

However, we couldn't speculate on a possible reason for the dispersion in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for BSSs from the same cluster. As discussed in Chapter 3, the potential dispersion in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in giant stars in this cluster was also found in previous studies, but it was mostly attributed to non-LTE effects. Further studies on $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ abundances of the BSSs are required to confirm our analysis.

5.6 Binary parameters of BSSs

A previous study utilized multi-epoch MUSE spectroscopy to study binary stars in the core of NGC 3201 ([23]). Using multiple radial velocity measurements for stars within five years of observations, they determined the probabilities of stars showing radial velocity variations. They discovered that at least $(57.5 \pm 7.9) \%$ of BSSs are in a binary system in the cluster's core. They provided binary system properties of 11 BSSs by fitting Keplerian orbits. We attempted to cross-match our BSSs with their data of these 11 BSSs and found four similar candidates. The results of this cross-match are provided in Table 5.1.

According to the previous study ([23]), B1 is identified as an extremely hard binary with a period less than a day, likely formed by mass transfer in a binary system. The minimum secondary mass (invisible mass) of 0.12 ± 0.01 solar masses ($M_{\odot} \sin(i)$) suggests that the companion may be an extremely low-mass white dwarf (ELM WD; [64]), which typically forms via Case A or early Case B mass transfer systems. However, the authors argue that mass transfer in a relatively wide BSS binary system (period > 100 days) is nearly impossible. Instead, they propose that such BSSs (B5, B6, and B7) formed via coalescence in systems with three or more stars during binary-binary or binary-single encounters.

We examined the atmospheric parameters of these four BSSs (see Table 1). The first three BSSs are all fast rotators (FRs) with temperatures exceeding 9000 K, while the fourth BSS is a slow-rotating star with a temperature of less than 8000 K. The orbital parameters suggests that FRs may also formed via coalescence in system with more than three stars in this cluster. This formation mechanism for FRs requires further investigation. While we have made an attempt to infer possible relationships between binary parameters from the previous study and atmospheric parameters derived in this work, no clear picture emerges regarding such a relationship.

Table 5.1: Binary system properties of four of our BSSs crossmatched with the data given in Table A.2 of [23].

BSS ID	Period (days)	Eccentricity	Amplitude (km/s)	Visible mass (M_{\odot})	Invisible mass ($M_{\odot} \sin(i)$)
B1	0.4706 ± 0.0001	0.01 ± 0.02	28.0 ± 0.8	1.20 ± 0.05	0.12 ± 0.01
B5	110.3 ± 0.3	0.04 ± 0.06	11.6 ± 0.7	1.20 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.03
B6	191 ± 3	0.06 ± 0.15	11.1 ± 1.5	1.20 ± 0.05	0.41 ± 0.07
B7	988 ± 75	0.11 ± 0.16	8.7 ± 1.7	1.20 ± 0.05	0.59 ± 0.14

Chapter 6

Conclusions

- We analyzed the spectra of 62 BSSs in the GC NGC 3201 and derived radial velocity, atmospheric parameters (effective temperature and surface gravity), and chemical abundances.
- We found many trends among the derived parameters supported by the previous study of BSSs in this cluster. Our approach towards deriving the parameters was different from others' approaches.
- FRs tend to be located towards the upper left side of the BSS sequence, suggesting recent BSS formation activity preferentially involved more massive primordial binaries.
- FRs tend to have higher radial velocities, possibly caused by orbital motion in binary systems or three- and four-body interactions occurring in the cluster's core.
- FRs tend to have higher temperatures, supporting the finding that they are located towards the upper left side of the BSS sequence.
- No trend was observed of atmospheric parameters with $\log g$ suggesting that surface gravity may not play a key role in the mass transfer process.
- No prominent trend of any chemical abundance (except $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) was found with the atmospheric parameters. This can be partially attributed to significant error estimates and non-LTE effects, which were not taken into account by the LTE assumptions in iSpec.
- The $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ values for the BSSs were found to be decreasing with increasing stellar temperature. This could be possibly attributed to the rise in opacity

caused by the abundance of partially ionized iron and its bound-bound transitions. An explanation for the dispersion in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ appears to be lacking at the present level. Other studies on the chemical abundances of BSSs in the cluster may help in obtaining a clearer picture of the relationships between chemical abundances and atmospheric parameters.

- Binary system properties for four of our BSSs were found by crossmatching with a previous study. The orbital parameters suggest that FRs may also form via coalescence in multiple-star systems in this cluster. This formation mechanism for FRs requires further investigation.
- There is no clear relationship emerging between binary parameters and atmospheric parameters for BSSs.

6.1 Future Work

This study utilized spectroscopy to derive atmospheric parameters and chemical abundances for the BSSs in NGC 3201. Additionally, a spectral energy distribution (SED) analysis can be conducted on various photometric data points spanning from UV to optical wavelengths for the BSSs in this cluster. This SED analysis has the potential to reveal estimates for effective temperature, luminosity, surface gravity, and radius. By performing both single and binary fits, valuable information can be obtained about the formation mechanism for BSSs, as well as the parameters of the companion star if the BSS is formed via mass transfer (see [13]; [14] for examples). Isochrone fitting can also be employed to derive mass and age estimates. The results of such a comprehensive SED analysis can significantly enhance the confidence in our findings and conclusions.

Appendices

.1 Table of Atmospheric Parameters

Table 1: Atmospheric parameters of the BSSs in NGC 3201. The radial velocity (RV), effective temperature (T_{eff}), and surface gravity ($\log g$) were determined using the methodology defined in the earlier chapter (4). The rotational velocity ($v \sin(i)$) values are obtained from the Cosmic-Lab website.

BSS ID	RV (km/s)	$v \sin(i)$ (km/s)	T_{eff} (K)	$\log g$
B1	495.49	89 ± 8	9289.57 ± 1124.68	3.47 ± 1.03
B2	503.52	5 ± 2	7205.99 ± 159.33	4.06 ± 0.08
B3	502.21	12 ± 2	7372.56 ± 507.38	4.59 ± 0.59
B4	511.07	149 ± 15	10342.10 ± 483.80	3.62 ± 0.54
B5	503.38	137 ± 12	10834.93 ± 1180.76	4.17 ± 1.18
B6	526.45	74 ± 7	9440.76 ± 4.11	5.00 ± 0.00
B7	482.51	13 ± 2	7443.09 ± 693.14	3.75 ± 0.44
B8	492.60	9 ± 1	7015.44 ± 120.40	3.85 ± 0.06
B9	493.97	5 ± 1	7124.58 ± 272.64	3.04 ± 0.06
B10	498.16	40 ± 4	8151.23 ± 638.13	3.50 ± 0.71
B11	498.02	5 ± 1	7442.96 ± 62.01	3.70 ± 0.40
B12	499.53	25 ± 2	8450.69 ± 874.34	3.18 ± 0.32
B13	507.22	5 ± 1	7450.75 ± 458.63	4.52 ± 0.69
B14	493.97	16 ± 3	7779.80 ± 524.83	3.68 ± 0.25
B15	496.45	5 ± 1	7290.97 ± 56.48	3.27 ± 0.21
B16	497.79	16 ± 3	8120.87 ± 392.95	3.96 ± 0.59
B17	493.97	5 ± 2	7259.23 ± 66.05	3.41 ± 0.01
B18	509.48	9 ± 3	7049.50 ± 71.40	4.56 ± 0.03
B19	497.79	5 ± 1	6857.26 ± 7.29	3.43 ± 0.02
B20	498.02	14 ± 2	8485.43 ± 374.61	3.25 ± 0.28
B21	488.24	20 ± 2	7385.12 ± 48.91	4.18 ± 0.23
B22	490.68	5 ± 2	7613.37 ± 164.06	3.33 ± 0.10
B23	523.75	100 ± 10	9214.55 ± 403.69	3.04 ± 0.24
B24	498.02	15 ± 2	7469.44 ± 122.51	3.99 ± 0.01
B25	499.70	36 ± 4	7805.26 ± 10.01	4.49 ± 0.01
B26	501.61	10 ± 3	7833.55 ± 279.03	3.50 ± 0.01
B27	495.69	35 ± 4	8386.41 ± 595.77	4.02 ± 0.79
B28	499.53	70 ± 5	9079.84 ± 112.91	3.87 ± 1.60
B29	510.14	50 ± 6	9184.72 ± 433.11	3.40 ± 0.00

Continued on next page

B30	522.60	62 ± 6	9959.68 ± 57.03	5.00 ± 0.00
B31	495.69	5 ± 2	7245.68 ± 151.34	3.45 ± 0.01
B32	545.68	207 ± 13	10000.00 ± 0.00	3.69 ± 0.03
B33	495.88	5 ± 2	7786.78 ± 108.58	3.43 ± 0.01
B34	503.38	9 ± 1	8317.04 ± 878.05	3.47 ± 0.04
B35	507.22	15 ± 1	7930.57 ± 220.02	3.50 ± 0.00
B36	528.59	82 ± 5	9818.95 ± 256.05	4.64 ± 0.52
B37	490.15	6 ± 2	7312.49 ± 3.48	3.50 ± 0.02
B38	541.83	80 ± 7	9976.27 ± 33.56	5.00 ± 0.00
B39	498.02	17 ± 3	7562.74 ± 234.44	4.46 ± 0.02
B40	503.38	13 ± 2	9122.61 ± 477.39	3.46 ± 0.01
B41	493.97	25 ± 3	8666.68 ± 859.71	3.41 ± 0.01
B42	510.28	45 ± 6	9373.46 ± 1.07	4.88 ± 0.17
B43	495.69	35 ± 4	7819.51 ± 170.71	3.99 ± 0.00
B44	504.13	5 ± 2	7453.28 ± 452.81	3.77 ± 0.52
B45	492.60	5 ± 2	7668.93 ± 36.88	3.34 ± 0.12
B46	503.52	5 ± 2	7853.02 ± 17.74	3.32 ± 0.16
B47	498.02	10 ± 1	8279.63 ± 575.25	3.36 ± 0.13
B48	498.36	26 ± 2	8520.08 ± 81.21	3.53 ± 0.11
B49	498.02	33 ± 4	7784.59 ± 284.43	3.41 ± 0.06
B50	501.61	5 ± 2	6952.57 ± 426.97	4.38 ± 0.59
B51	501.84	5 ± 1	7557.61 ± 693.49	4.12 ± 0.12
B52	499.92	80 ± 8	10219.04 ± 451.19	4.71 ± 0.33
B53	499.53	27 ± 3	8407.66 ± 448.97	3.45 ± 0.07
B54	498.28	23 ± 5	8180.33 ± 626.60	4.44 ± 0.47
B55	496.96	18 ± 3	7801.79 ± 224.53	3.74 ± 0.34
B56	502.12	0 ± 2	6963.39 ± 18.45	4.94 ± 0.08
B57	499.53	41 ± 4	8883.85 ± 164.27	4.25 ± 1.06
B58	495.69	13 ± 2	8444.76 ± 158.99	3.45 ± 0.09
B59	499.22	5 ± 2	8277.64 ± 686.45	3.96 ± 0.65
B60	507.22	17 ± 3	8693.24 ± 126.39	3.49 ± 0.11
B61	501.61	5 ± 2	7576.54 ± 620.65	3.52 ± 0.07
B62	509.25	0 ± 3	8183.74 ± 808.17	3.75 ± 0.35

.2 Table of Chemical Abundances

Table 2: Chemical abundances of the BSSs in NGC 3201. The methodology for abundance estimation is defined in the earlier chapter (4). In cases where we couldn't obtain a proper abundance estimate, we have placed "...".

BSS ID	[Fe/H]	[Ni/Fe]	[Cu/Fe]	[Na/Fe]	[Mg/Fe]	[Ti/Fe]
B1	-2.28 ± 0.40	-0.66	0.00	0.42	0.53 ± 0.57	-0.64 ± 1.12
B2	-1.53 ± 0.21	-2.16	-2.07	-0.94	0.42 ± 0.61	0.37 ± 0.49
B3	-1.90 ± 0.56	1.57	1.92	-3.48	0.85 ± 0.08	-0.86 ± 2.01
B4	-2.46 ± 0.42	...	0.00	...	0.95 ± 1.34	0.20 ± 1.08
B5	-1.66 ± 0.78	...	0.00	0.00	1.41 ± 1.22	-0.56 ± 0.78
B6	-2.31 ± 0.00	-0.95	2.62	-3.05	0.15 ± 0.40	-1.88 ± 0.42
B7	-1.52 ± 0.31	0.00	-6.23	-1.06	1.23 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.05
B8	-1.53 ± 0.43	-2.82	-2.37	-1.46	0.49 ± 0.09	0.88 ± 0.28
B9	-1.25 ± 0.23	-2.60	0.72	-1.15	0.61 ± 0.13	0.48 ± 0.09
B10	-2.07 ± 0.95	2.88	-2.99	-1.49	1.32 ± 0.23	-0.55 ± 1.23
B11	-1.77 ± 0.54	0.58	-2.03	1.58	1.39 ± 0.39	0.51 ± 0.03
B12	-2.19 ± 0.59	-0.15	-0.95	...	0.82 ± 0.42	-1.10 ± 1.70
B13	-1.58 ± 0.50	-1.83	-2.02	-1.36	0.87 ± 0.26	0.79 ± 0.23
B14	-1.90 ± 0.95	-1.55	-1.89	-1.98	0.98 ± 0.41	-0.80 ± 1.50
B15	-1.69 ± 0.47	-2.19	-1.69	-1.03	0.22 ± 0.22	-1.22 ± 1.75
B16	-2.14 ± 0.00	-1.26	-1.53	-0.73	0.47 ± 0.00	-1.22 ± 2.79
B17	-1.75 ± 0.49	-1.44	-1.59	1.25	0.31 ± 0.10	-0.79 ± 0.81
B18	-1.36 ± 0.27	0.62	0.60	-2.1	0.65 ± 0.22	-1.17 ± 2.39
B19	-1.66 ± 0.45	-2.05	-0.12	1.15	0.64 ± 0.10	-1.37 ± 2.43
B20	-2.10 ± 0.59	-0.81	-0.88	-0.13	0.39 ± 0.23	0.44 ± 0.04
B21	-1.75 ± 0.63	-0.65	-1.42	...	0.45 ± 0.56	0.52 ± 0.34
B22	-1.74 ± 0.79	-1.74	-0.83	-1.22	0.05 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.14
B23	-2.71 ± 0.18	-0.89	...	-5.02	0.39 ± 0.33	-0.08 ± 1.89
B24	-1.89 ± 0.98	-1.56	1.86	...	1.04 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.71
B25	-1.66 ± 0.11	-1.56	-4.85	-0.80	0.50 ± 0.57	-0.38 ± 1.69
B26	-1.53 ± 0.33	-0.73	-1.38	-5.18	0.96 ± 0.61	0.37 ± 0.05
B27	-1.89 ± 0.53	-1.58	-1.00	-0.54	1.22 ± 0.68	0.21 ± 0.09
B28	-2.01 ± 0	-0.87	-0.60	-5.02	0.86 ± 1.14	-0.57 ± 1.15
B29	-2.15 ± 0.57	-1.03	...	-7.29	-0.33 ± 1.23	-1.94 ± 0.03
B30	-2.5 ± 0.33	1.69	2.07	-1.16	-0.34 ± 2.21	-0.42 ± 1.39

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B31	-1.53 ± 0.52	-1.36	-1.92	1.70	0.20 ± 0.45	0.26 ± 0.22
B32	-1.8 ± 0.43	0.82	0.00	0.24	-1.36 ± 0.81	-0.5 ± 1.87
B33	-1.63 ± 0.58	-1.02	-1.07	-1.39	0.21 ± 0.06	0.01 ± 0.22
B34	-1.41 ± 0.31	2.22	1.98	-1.43	0.21 ± 0.11	-0.09 ± 0.61
B35	-2.89 ± 0.00	-1.62	1.90	-0.76	-0.24 ± 1.42	0.55 ± 0.13
B36	-2.24 ± 0.29	-0.56	-2.25	...	0.59 ± 0.24	0.95 ± 0.04
B37	-1.64 ± 0.36	-1.74	1.20	-1.32	0.88 ± 0.04	0.34 ± 0.64
B38	-2.35 ± 0.88	3.10	2.36	0.07	0.22 ± 1.95	-0.67 ± 1.60
B39	-1.69 ± 0.23	-0.07	1.66	...	0.33 ± 0.53	-0.96 ± 3.22
B40	-2.13 ± 0.07	1.67	-0.19	0.00	-1.16 ± 3.39	-0.64 ± 2.50
B41	-1.96 ± 0.31	0.00	-0.50	0.76	0.59 ± 0.06	0.55 ± 0.04
B42	-2.13 ± 0.50	-0.43	-0.57	-2.13	-0.25 ± 0.04	-2.41 ± 0.51
B43	-1.34 ± 0.23	-3.02	-1.95	-1.40	0.40 ± 0.61	-2.29 ± 0.31
B44	-1.38 ± 0.21	-2.01	-1.59	-2.14	0.84 ± 0.22	0.32 ± 0.39
B45	-1.73 ± 0.50	-1.01	-1.40	1.42	0.08 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.04
B46	-1.81 ± 0.17	-1.73	-1.56	1.89	0.03 ± 0.37	0.77 ± 0.22
B47	-2.28 ± 0.55	1.67	-1.35	1.36	0.50 ± 0.40	0.07 ± 0.17
B48	-2.34 ± 0.94	-2.36	-1.51	-0.71	0.85 ± 0.08	-0.62 ± 0.40
B49	-1.42 ± 0.60	-0.06	-1.76	-0.63	0.48 ± 0.04	-0.99 ± 1.46
B50	-1.51 ± 0.56	-1.49	-2.25	-1.56	0.74 ± 0.29	1.11 ± 0.52
B51	-1.89 ± 0.66	-2.19	2.25	-1.08	1.18 ± 0.18	-3.69 ± 0.04
B52	-2.43 ± 0.17	-0.36	0.09	...	-0.75 ± 1.24	-0.60 ± 0.16
B53	-2.71 ± 0.26	-0.41	-1.88	2.62	0.34 ± 0.45	0.89 ± 0.01
B54	-1.06 ± 0.00	-2.51	-1.50	-4.12	1.65 ± 1.17	-0.92 ± 1.92
B55	-1.6 ± 0.52	-0.78	-1.48	-0.76	0.75 ± 0.11	-1.24 ± 3.27
B56	-1.26 ± 0.03	-2.05	-2.39	-0.11	0.27 ± 0.33	-0.62 ± 3.29
B57	-2.46 ± 0.38	-1.70	-0.51	3.40	0.04 ± 1.89	-1.2 ± 1.68
B58	-2.37 ± 0.60	-0.51	-0.92	2.30	0.21 ± 1.04	-0.1 ± 0.75
B59	-1.52 ± 0.15	1.55	-1.31	-0.85	0.52 ± 0.23	-1.12 ± 2.27
B60	-2.40 ± 0.58	-0.40	-1.35	0.74	0.19 ± 0.88	-1.23 ± 2.87
B61	-1.73 ± 0.67	-1.44	-1.56	1.46	1.15 ± 0.00	-0.36 ± 0.98
B62	-1.94 ± 0.88	1.93	-1.32	-0.52	0.56 ± 1.11	-0.36 ± 2.44

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